

Shannon's Entropy, Number of Arrangements and Conservation of Information

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In a previous note (1), we argued that information = $-\ln(P_i)$, where P_i is the probability for the i th letter in the 26 letter English alphabet to appear in a long message, may be obtained by considering "interactions" which leave P_i unchanged as the initial message undergoes interactions until it reaches a destination. $-\ln(P_i)$ then naturally appears as a conserved quantity in the interactions which ensure that P_i does not change as one moves from source to destination. Thus, each letter contains a substance $-\ln(P_i)$, called information, which is similar to the energy of a particle in a gas. An interaction may change one letter into another, but the overall information of a long message cannot change because otherwise P_i would change.

In the literature (2), (3), there are descriptions of $-\ln(P_i)$ as being associated with different arrangements of the same letters in a long message. In this note, we try to show how the conserved quantity $-\ln(P_i)$ is linked to ideas of arrangements of letters.

Arrangements of Letters

In (2), arrangements of independent letters, each with its own probability of occurrence P_i is considered as the starting point to obtaining Shannon's entropy. In such a case, an arrangement consists of N letters where N approaches infinite (i.e. is a very large number). For example, one may use the 26 letter English alphabet and the letter "a" would have a probability of P_1 of appearing in the message or would appear NP_1 times etc.

In (1), K is the number of different arrangements which may be made of an N letter long string and is given as:

$$K = \binom{N}{NP_1} \binom{N-NP_1}{NP_2} \dots \binom{N-NP_1-NP_2-\dots-NP_{25}}{NP_{26}} \quad ((1))$$

Where $\binom{N}{x} = \frac{N!}{x!(N-x)!}$

Next, Stirling's approximation is applied, yielding:

$$\ln(1/K) = -N \sum_i P_i \ln(P_i) \quad ((2))$$

One may note that $1/K$ is the probability to have a particular arrangement if all arrangements have the same probability. Thus, the probability for any particular arrangement is minus Shannon's entropy.

Linking Arrangement Arrangements with Probability

In the above section, Stirling's approximation was applied to large $n!$ terms, but one may obtain ((2)) without the use of this approximation. It should be noted that in Shannon's original

approach of finding information $\ln(P_i)$ (3) and in the reaction-conserved quantity approach (1), $\ln(P_i)$ appears “naturally” without “ln” being introduced via Stirling’s approximation.

Consider various permutations of a very long list of N English alphabet letters, each having a probability of P_i of appearing, i.e. there are $N P_1$ “a”s etc as given in the section above. Then, there are K arrangements each with the same weight, so the normalized probability of any arrangement is $1/K$.

Next, consider choosing a particular letter j which has probability P_j . Imagine adding a second letter k with probability P_k following it, where k could be j . Next, consider that j can be any letter. What is the total probability of all such two letter arrangements?

$$\sum_j P_j \sum_k P_k = 1 \quad ((3))$$

This may be continued for strings of N letters. Thus, the product of probabilities is normalized. Consider as in (3), the probability for an arrangement of letters where there are $N P_j$ occurrences of letter j . Then, the normalized probability (as given in (3)) is:

$$\text{Probability} = \text{Product over } j P_j^{N P_j} = \exp \left\{ \sum_j [N P_j \ln(P_j)] \right\} \quad ((4))$$

This probability may be equated to $1/K$ where K is the number of arrangements yielding:

$$1/K = \exp \left\{ \sum_j [N P_j \ln(P_j)] \right\} \quad \text{or} \quad -\ln(K) = \sum_j N P_j \ln(P_j) \quad ((5))$$

Thus, ((2)) is obtained.

Interaction Model

In (1), we suggested that information $\ln(P_i)$ appears as a conserved quantity in an “interaction picture”. Consider a message of N letters at an initial point with a P_i the probability distribution for each letter i . If at the destination, P_i is unchanged, even if some letters are “changed” during transmission, we argue there should be a conserved quantity. We would like to note that in (2), it is stated that if one has two different probability distributions P_i and Q_i initially and one sends a message (or a coded message), at the destination one should be able to distinguish if the original message followed P_i or Q_i . For example, P_i might apply to English and Q_i to French. Thus it seems that in (2), P_i and Q_i are preserved during transmission. For this to be the case, we argue the initial message has a certain amount of a conserved substance which we call $f(P_i)$ i.e. letter “a” has $f(P_1)$ of this substance. It is possible that a letter “a” undergoes an interaction during transmission and changes into letter j . Some substance is lost and must appear somewhere else. If one considers time reversal balance, then:

$$f(P_i) = f(P_j) + \text{lost or gained substance} \quad ((6))$$

Consider the “lost” case and the substance to be like a photon and $f(P_i)$ like the energy of an electron. Then an electron drops from level i to j giving off a photon. The time reversed balance is: a photon combines with P_j yielding P_i . In terms of probability, we argue this is:

$$P_i = P_j \text{ Probability(“photon” with missing substance) } \quad ((7))$$

Taking \ln of both sides of ((7)) yields: $\ln(P_i) = \ln(P_j) + \ln(\text{Prob of photon}) \quad ((8))$

Thus, $\ln(P_i)$ is the conserved substance which is usually called “information”

If one does not like the idea of time reversal, consider the case that for every letter i which becomes a j , a j must become an i with the same probability to conserve P_i .

Thus, given a probability distribution P_i , there is automatically a conserved quantity (information) of $\ln(P_i)$ associated with each “letter” i . Not only that, but for large sequences of letters, the total amount of information (conserved) quantity is fixed by the distribution P_i and the number of letters N i.e. Fixed amount of information for a given $P_i = N \sum \text{over } i P_i \ln(P_i)$. Thus, if one has P_i for English and Q_i for French, each has its own intrinsic amount of information or conserved quantity.

How is the amount of information (conserved quantity) related to the number of arrangements of letters? It is shown in ((5)), that $1/K$, where K is the number of arrangements of letters, equals: $\text{Product over } i P_i^{N P_i}$. From ((8)), however, $P_i = \exp(\ln(P_i))$ is a solution, which also follows directly without ((8)). Thus, the conserved quantity or information of each letter to the power of e is the probability for that letter to occur. Then, $\exp(\text{total information}) = 1/K$, the probability for any arrangement.

Analogy with Physics

The description above of two languages with probabilities P_i and Q_i for each letter is like a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas with two different temperatures T_1 and T_2 . The distribution for each is different, but each $f(e_i, T_i)$ is proportional to $\exp(-e_i/T_i)$. Thus, $-e_i/T_i$ is the information $\ln(f(e_i))$. It is also a conserved quantity. This may be generalized to include the normalization constant i.e. $\ln(f(e_i)) = -(e_i - u)/T$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to describe approaches to information theory which link Shannon’s entropy to the \ln of the number of arrangements of letters to a conserved quantity, information = $\ln(P_i)$. For a given probability distribution, each letter has a probability P_i and an information substance amount of $\ln(P_i)$. Thus, for a string of N (N being a very large number), the number of “a’s” is given by $N P_i$, but the information (conserved substance) is $N \ln(P_i)$. Thus, N and P_i fix the amount of information in a given system. Interactions may occur which change some letters into others, but if P_i is to be preserved at the destination, $N \sum \text{over } i P_i \ln(P_i)$ must be constant.

Product over i $P_i^{N P_i}$ is the normalized probability for any arrangement of N letters (N large) thus it equals $1/K$ where K is the number of arrangements. Product over i $P_i^{N P_i}$, however, is $\exp[\text{Sum over } i \text{ } P_i \ln(P_i)] = \exp(\text{Shannon's entropy}) = \exp(\text{total amount of information})$.

References

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